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Sustainable development through workforce planning: Forecasting workforce demand for the industrial sector from 2007 to 2016

ABSTRACT

This paper presents and discusses the results of a study on workforce forecasting for the industrial sector from 2007 to 2016. The workforce demand is estimated based on past investment and employment generation data. Two mathematical models were developed in order to forecast the future demand of the workforce at the national level and export processing zone level. An indicator called employment creation per investment was developed for the study. The data was collected from the Ministry of Investment Promotion since 1985 on investments and employment creation.

Keywords: Workforce planning, Forecasting, Investment, Workforce supply and demand

1 INTRODUCTION

Human resource planning is a process of identifying the quantity and quality of employees required to achieve goals and strategic objectives. Therefore, human resource planning ensures that the right number of people are in the right jobs at the right time to meet the set goals and objectives. Human resource planning is vital at both the national and organizational levels. At the national level, a well-planned human resource is seen as the foundation for economic growth (Buchan 2004; Clarke and Carr-Hill, 2001; Campbell, 1997; Gill, 1996). At the organizational level, human resource planning identifies the number of retirements for a future given period, identifies gaps between current and the required skills to perform work during a future given period, and could provide valuable information to maintain a diversified human resource with expected quantity and quality (Mamman and Akuratiyagamage, 2005; Wickramasinghe, 2006). Such information is vital to prepare plans for organizational expansions and the restructuring of human resources.

The workforce planning for sustainable economic development has become one of the challenges faced by nations today. For effective workforce planning, the foundation is the identification of the supply and demand of labour. Then measures could be taken to address surplus and shortage in the short run as well as in the long run. Though forecasting human resources based on a model is essential, to date, no study has been carried out to estimate workforce requirements at the national level in Sri Lanka. Therefore, this study is an attempt to address this research gap.

The purpose of the research was to estimate workforce demand of the industrial sector for the years 2007

to 2016 based on past investment and employment generation data. It is expected that the methodology adopted in this research demonstrates the originality of the theory. Further, it is expected that the findings of this study will have broader relevance at the national level of policy planning.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the research background of this study. Sections 3 and 4 explain methodology, data analysis, and findings, respectively. Conclusions are given in section 5.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Workforce Planning

Economic development and employment are the areas that extend across both the government sector and private sector, where strong partnerships are required among government institutions, non-government organizations, industry groups, employment services, training providers, and communities. Such a partnership will contribute to the development of policies and programs that will enable the government sector and private sector to meet their objectives most optimally (Hamilton et al, 2000; Jayaraman and Singh, 2007).

The demand for the workforce should be forecasted to manage the supply side of the workforce. If there is a shortage in workforce supply, it would be difficult to carry out development activities according to the planned or targeted levels. Gap analysis is the process of comparing the workforce supply projection to the workforce demand forecast. An analysis should consider the composition of the workforce, including demographic characteristics, geographic location, size, and employee

skill levels. Such an analysis would show either a shortage or a surplus in workforce supply. A shortage (when projected supply is less than forecasted demand) indicates a future shortage of needed workers, while a surplus (when projected supply is greater than forecasted demand) indicates a future excess in some categories of workers. Surplus leads to unemployment creation, while shortage leads to failure in implementing plans at the micro or macro levels. Therefore, both surplus and shortage situations require action (Hall, 1986; Hamilton et al, 2000; Williams, 1998). Hence, challenges related to the workforce are difficult to overcome with ad-hoc planning; it needs a proper analysis with greater insight.

2.2 Sri Lankan Context

Sri Lanka needs a systematic human resource assessment to execute better development planning. Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the plot of past data on total investments and total employment created, respectively.

Figure 1: Total Investment 1990-2006

When the total investment of the year 2002 is considered, the breakdown of investments by sector is as follows. Agriculture and fisheries 34.5%, Manufacturing 16.5%, Construction 4.4%, Trade and hotels 14.7%, Transport and communication 4.7%, Finance and insurance 2.6%, and personnel services 22.7%. Therefore, the macro scenario presented in Figure 1 does not provide much detail on micro-level features. Hence, the development of a model for investment-based workforce planning at both macro and micro levels is essential.

Figure 2: Total Employment 1990-2005

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Sources of Data

Investment and employment generation data were collected from the Ministry of Enterprise Development and Investment Promotions. This paper presents the results of the analysis at two levels. That is the total export processing zone (EPZ) level and the Katunayake EPZ level. Table 1 shows the details of the data used for the analysis in this paper.

Table 1: Details of data used for the analysis

Data category	Details	Duration
Total EPZ	Total investment, employment, and the number of firms in operation.	1985-2006
Katunayake	Total investment, employment, and the number of firms in operation.	1985-2006

In the study, a model was developed to forecast the workforce for the years 2007 to 2016 based on the investment and employment generation data for the years 1985 to 2006.

3.2 Methods of Data Analysis

3.2.1 Employment Creation per Investment (ECI)

In the industrial sector, employment creation exclusively depends on the investments made under a particular project or sector. Therefore, an indicator called employment creation per investment (ECI) was calculated for the study to model the relationship between investment and employment creation. ECI was developed based on past investment and employment generation data obtained from 1985 to 2006. ECI value is used to forecast the workforce for the years 2007 to 2016. ECI is defined as:

$$ECI = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{n=Total} (Jobs)}{\sum_{n=1}^{n=Total} (Investment)}$$

Where n is the selected subcategory number in a selected segment. For example, the segment can be considered as one EPZ. Sub-categories will be the industrial projects coming under that particular EPZ. Then, if the value of investment is given, employment creation can be estimated using this indicator. Moreover, it is assumed that the same principle can be applied to the macro-level scenario as well.

3.2.2 Best Fitted Model

It is a common practice to "fit a line" to a set of data to determine some useful parameters in a mathematical

model or perhaps to generate a calibration curve. A straight line is a simple polynomial, and the goal of the fit is to determine the coefficients (the slope and intercept) of the polynomial that lead to the "best fit" of a line to the data. However, when the data is nonlinear, it needs higher-order modeling. The fitting process can be generalized to determine the coefficients of a higher-order polynomial that best fits the data points. In this research, the analysis is limited to first-order (Linear) and second-order (Quadratic) models.

First order (Linear) polynomial is defined as:

$$Y = a + bt$$

Where t is the time and y is the model output. Here, a and b give the coefficients of the model fitted with the data.

The second order (Quadratic model), polynomial is defined as:

$$Y = a + bt + ct^2$$

Where a , b , and c denote the coefficients of the quadratic model fitted with the data.

4 Data Analysis and Findings

4.1 ECI for 1995-2005

Figure 3 shows the calculated ECI for the ten years from 1995 to 2005 for the country (Macro level). The average value of ECI for that period is 1559 [Jobs/mUS \$]

Figure 3: ECI [US \$ 1 million] at Macro Level

Figure 4 shows the calculated ECI for the 10 years from 1995 to 2005 for the total EPZ data (Micro level). The average ECI value is 328 [Jobs/m US\$].

Figure 4: ECI [US \$ 1 million] for total EPZ

Figure 5 shows the calculated ECI for the ten years from 1995 to 2005 for the total Katunayake EPZ level (another micro level). The average ECI value is 508 [Jobs/mUS\$]

Figure 5: ECI [US \$ 1 million] for Katunayake EPZ

Figure 6 shows the future investment predictions for the macro level data, i.e., in the Sri Lankan context at large, for the year 2006 to 2015 with linear and quadratic models.

Figure 6: Predictions of Macro Level Investment in Sri Lanka [in US \$ million]

Fitted models are as follows:

Linear model (First order model):

$$Y(t) = 21.8252t + 190.5973 \text{ with } adj R^2 = 87.6$$

Quadratic Model (Second-order model)

$$Y(t) = 1.9685t^2 - 1.7963t + 241.7772 \text{ with } adj R^2 = 86.6$$

Investment predictions for some selected years are given in Table 2. In the year 2010, an investment worth US\$ 525 could be expected under the linear model. ECI for the year 2010 is 1559. The expected number of

employment generations in the year 2010 will be given by the value 1559 x 525 based on the linear model.

Table 2 Forecasted Investments for Sri Lanka (for selected years)

Year	Linear Model [US \$ m]	Second-order model [US \$ m]
2008	490	600
2010	525	700
2014	625	925
2016	675	1100

The expected future employment generation for some selected years based on the ECI indicator at the county level is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Forecasted Employment Generation (for some selected years)

Year	Linear Model	Quadratic model
2008	763,910	935,400
2010	818,475	1,091,300
2014	974,375	1,442,075
2016	1,052,325	1,714,900

Figure 7 shows the possible future investment predictions at the total EPZ level, i.e., a selected micro level segment.

Figure 7: Predictions of Total Investment in IPZs [in US \$ million]

The data was also analyzed for the micro-level segment of Katunayake EPZ. Using the same procedure, linear and quadratic models were generated. It is found that the quadratic model gives the best performance, and the coefficients were $X = 63 + 5484t - 125t^2$, where t and X denote the time in years and the number of employment creation, respectively. For the quadratic model, fitting accuracy for the data for the Katunayake industrial processing zone was 98.7%, while for the linear model, fitting accuracy was 85.4%. Similarly, results could be obtained for other industrial processing zones.

5 CONCLUSIONS

For the study, an indicator called ECI was created. Based on ECI, employment generation is forecasted for the years 2007 to 2016. The methodology adopted in this study could be applied to forecast employment creation based on past investment data of any other given sector of a country. For example, the hotel industry would be one of the possible micro-level segments. Further, another study can be carried out at the national level, where the total workforce requirement for the service sectors could be forecasted.

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